

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Four

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 4:0 For the choir director; on stringed instruments. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַחַת בְּנִינּוֹת מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : 2</p>
<p>Psa. 4:1 Answer me when I call, O God of my righteousness! You have relieved me in my distress; Be gracious to me and hear my prayer.</p>	<p>בְּקִרְאֵי עֲנֵנִי וְאֱלֹהֵי צְדִיקִי בַצָּר הִרְתַּבְּתָּ לִּי חֲנֻנִי וְשָׁמַעַתְּ פִּלְתֵּי : 3</p>
<p>Psa. 4:2 O sons of men, how long will my honor become a reproach? <i>How long</i> will you love what is worthless and aim at deception? Selah.</p> <p>³ But know that the LORD has set apart the godly man for Himself; The LORD hears when I call to Him.</p>	<p>בְּנֵי אִישׁ עַד-מָה כְּבוֹדִי לְכִלְמָה תֵּאֱהָבוּן רֵיק תִּבְקָשׁוּ כֶּזֶב סִלָּה : 4</p> <p>וְדַעוּ כִּי-הַפְלָתָה יְהוָה תְּסִיד לֹא יִהְיֶה וְשָׁמַעַתְּ בְּקִרְאֵי אֱלֹהֵי : 5 רְגֹזוּ וְאֵל-תִּתְחַטְּאוּ אִמְרוּ בְּלִבְבְּכֶם עַל-מִשְׁכַּבְכֶם וְדַמּוּ סִלָּה : 6 זְבַחַי זְבַח־צְדִיק וּבְטָחוּ אֶל-יְהוָה : 7</p>
<p>Psa. 4:4 Tremble, and do not sin; Meditate in your heart upon your bed, and be still. Selah.</p> <p>⁵ Offer the sacrifices of righteousness, And trust in the LORD.</p>	<p>רַבִּים אִמְרִים מִי-יִרְאֶנּוּ טוֹב נִסְחָה עָלֵינוּ אֹר פְּנֵיךָ יְהוָה : 8 נִתְתַּחַת שִׁמְתָה בְּלִבִּי מַעַת דְּגָנָם וְתִירוֹשָׁם רַבּוּ : 9 בְּשִׁלּוֹם יִתְדוּ אֲשַׁכְּבָה וְאִישָׁן כִּי-אַתָּה יְהוָה לְבָרַד לְבִטָּח תוֹשִׁיבֵנִי :</p>
<p>Psa. 4:6 Many are saying, "Who will show us <i>any</i> good?" Lift up the light of Your countenance upon us, O LORD!</p> <p>⁷ You have put gladness in my heart, More than when their grain and new wine abound.</p> <p>⁸ In peace I will both lie down and sleep, For You alone, O LORD, make me to dwell in safety.</p>	

Targum

Psa. 4:1 For praise, with melodies. A hymn of David. ² At the time of my prayer, accept [it] from me, O God of my righteousness; at the time of distress, you relieved me; pity me and accept my prayer. ³ O sons of men, why is my glory for humiliation? You will love vanity; you will seek falsehood forever. ⁴ And they knew, for the LORD has separated the righteous man for himself; the LORD will accept the prayer of David when he calls to him. ⁵ Tremble for him, and do not sin; utter your petition with your mouth and your request in your heart; and pray upon your beds and remember the days of death forever. ⁶ Subdue your impulses and it will be reckoned to you as a righteous sacrifice; and hope in the LORD. ⁷ Many say, "Who will show us good?" Lift on us the light of your countenance, O LORD. ⁸ You have placed joy in my heart when their grain and their wine has increased. ⁹ In peace I both lay down and sleep, because you alone are the LORD; in security you will make me dwell.

Interlinear

Psa. 4:0 For the choir director on stringed instruments

Lex

Lex Trl

A Psalm of David

Psa. 4:1 Answer me when I call

Lex

Lex Trl

עֲנֵה

ʿanah

קָרָא

qaraʾ

O God of my righteousness You have

אֱלֹהִים

ʾelohim

צְדָק

tzedeq

relieved me in my distress Be gracious to me

רָחַב

rachav

צָר

tzar

חַנּוּן

chanan

and hear my prayer

שָׁמַע

shamaʿ

תְּפִלָּה

tefillah

Psa. 4:2 O sons of men how long

Lex

Lex Trl

בְּנֵי

ben

אִישׁ

ʾish

מָה

mah

עַד

ʿad

will my honor become a reproach How long

כְּבוֹד

kavod

כְּלִמָּה

kelimmah

will you love what is worthless and aim at deception

אָהַב

ʾahav

רִיק

riq

רִיק

riq

בָּקָשׁ

baqash

כָּזָב

kazav

Selah

סָלָה
selah

Psa. 4:3 But know that the Lord has set apart
Lex יָדַע יהוה פָּלָה פָּלָה
Lex Trl yada^c yhwh palah palah

the godly man for Himself The Lord
חָסִיד חָסִיד יהוה
chasid chasid yhwh

hears when I call to Him
שָׁמַע קָרָא
shama^c qara^b

Psa. 4:4 Tremble
Lex רָגַז
Lex Trl ragaz

and do not sin Meditate in
חָטָא אָמַר
chata^b amar

your heart upon your bed and be still Selah
לֵבָב מִשְׁכָּב דָּמַם סָלָה
levav mishkav damam selah

Psa. 4:5 Offer the sacrifices of righteousness
Lex זָבַח זָבַח צְדָקָה
Lex Trl zavach zevach tzedeq

And trust in the Lord
בָּטַח יהוה
batach yhwh

Psa. 4:6 Many are saying
Lex רַב אָמַר
Lex Trl rav amar

Who will show us any good Lift up
מִי רָאָה טוֹב נָשָׂא
mi ra^aah tov nasa^b

the light of Your countenance upon us O Lord
אור פְּנִים יהוה
ʾor panim yhwh

Psa. 4:7 You have put gladness in my heart
Lex נָתַן שְׂמֵחָה לֵב
Lex Trl natan simchah lev

More than when their grain and new wine
מִן מִן עֵת דָּגָן תִּירוֹשׁ תִּירוֹשׁ
min min et dagan tirosh tirosh

abound
רָבַב
ravav

Psa. 4:8 In peace I will both lie down and
Lex שְׁלוֹם יָחַד שָׁכַב שָׁכַב
Lex Trl shalom yachad shakhav shakhav

sleep For You alone O Lord
יָשַׁן בָּדָד יְהוָה
yashen badad yhwh

make me to dwell in safety
יָשַׁב בֶּטַח
yashav betach

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
For the choir director; on stringed instruments. A Psalm of David.	לְמִנְצַחַת בְּנִגְיֹנוֹת מְזֻמָּר לְדָוִד :

Verse Analysis

David wrote this Psalm while he was fleeing from his first-born Absalom. The Psalm was addressed to David's enemies. David told them to improve their ethics and morality. David declared that Absalom was immoral for revolting against him. A divine decree from the LORD made David King of Israel. Therefore, an attempt to overthrow the King was a sin against the LORD.

Absalom's revolt was due to David's loss of compassion for the LORD's people. The Bathsheba incident caused him to forget that the LORD made him King because of his kindness. David was only caring about himself. The revolt reminded David that he let the Nefesh take over.

לְמִנְצַחַת בְּנִגְיֹנוֹת (lam' natzecha ben'geenot) – means "victorious music." This Psalm is a call to the Sefirah Netzach. David believed that the power of music elevates the Ruach to be able to call upon the Sefirot. Netzach can give a person the strength to overcome anything that might disturb his inner peace and serenity.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory through music, a Psalm of David.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Answer me when I call, O God of my righteousness! You have relieved me in my distress; Be gracious to me and hear my prayer.</p>	<p>בְּקִרְאֵי עֲנֵנִי אֱלֹהֵי צְדִקְתִּי בְּצָר הִרְתַּבַּת לִי חַנּוּנִי וּשְׁמַע תְּפִלָּתִי :</p>

Verse Analysis

בְּקִרְאֵי עֲנֵנִי (b'kar' ee anaynee) means "proclaim and answer." David offered his prayer and did not demand an immediate answer. David knew that the Shekinah was always close to him and will hear his cry. He let his distress go because he felt the Shekinah with him.

Prayer is victory over distress. Through the power of reasoning, one can discern what is right and true. One must turn to one's knowledge of the LORD as the sole source of the fulfillment of one's desires that one must pledge whatever good the LORD may send so that the LORD's Will would be done in Malkhut.

The vindication David wanted was from the false accusations that Absalom accused him of.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

When I pray LORD, I know you will vindicate me because you have taken away my distress in the past.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
2 O sons of men, how long will my honor become a reproach? <i>How long</i> will you love what is worthless and aim at deception? Selah.	בְּנֵי אִישׁ עַד-מָה כְּבוֹדִי לְכִלְמָה תֵּאֱהָבוּ רֵיק תִּבְקָשׁוּ כְזָב סֵלָה :

Verse Analysis

בְּנֵי אִישׁ (b'nay eesh) means "sons of man." David used this phrase to redirect his remarks from the LORD to humans. David's enemies ridiculed him for calling upon the LORD to help him to defeat his enemies. David's enemies felt prayer itself is a form of self-deception and weakness. These men did not value prayer.

תֵּאֱהָבוּ רֵיק (tehehhavon reek) means "empty love." All of a person's ways and deeds are worthless if they do not bring one closer to the LORD.

אִישׁ (ish) – means "man." This word denotes a superior man.

אָדָם (adam) – means "man." This word denotes an ordinary man.

David understood the significance of respecting the monarchy with honor and dignity.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Sons of great men, how long will you respect the monarchy? You love vanity and seek deception. Pause and meditate on this verse.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ But know that the LORD has ^{1a}set apart the ^bgodly man for Himself; The LORD ^chears when I call to Him.</p>	<p>וְדַעוּ כִּי־הִפָּלֵה יְהוָה תָּסִיד לִי יְהוָה יִשְׁמַע בְּקוֹלִי אֱלֹהֵי :</p>

Verse Analysis

Experience has shown that one should not close one's eyes to what the LORD will do. The Sefirah Chesed will send mercy to all who demonstrate trust in the LORD without reservations.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Know that Chesed will shower people devoted to the LORD its love and mercy, and Chesed will listen when prayer is offered.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
4 Tremble, and do not sin; Meditate in your heart upon your bed, and be still. Selah.	רָגַזוּ וְאַל-תִּהְיוּ טְאֵוֹת אִמְרוּ בְּלִבְבְּכֶם עַל-מִשְׁכַּבְּכֶם וְדַמּוּ סֵלָה

Verse Analysis

רָגַזוּ (reeg'zo) means "be agitated, quiver, quake, be excited, perturbed." This word connotes that he who prays can hope for the Shekinah's nearness throughout one's life. A person can feel the Neshamah, which is a part of the soul.

Homiletically, the verse means that Israel is urged to tremble from the specter of sin to the point where sin becomes disturbing and traumatic. When one goes to sleep, one can think with clarity and objectively because one abandons one's daily pursuits. Forget about the material world and concentrate on the spiritual world.

One should arouse their good inclination to battle evil inclination.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Depart quickly from sinning and sin no more. When you prepare to sleep on your bed, let go of the material world and concentrate on the Spiritual world. Meditate upon this verse.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
⁵ Offer the sacrifices of righteousness, And trust in the LORD.	זָבַחְתָּו זִבְחֵי-צֶדֶק וּבִטְחוֹ אֶל-יְהוָה׃

Verse Analysis

זָבַחְתָּו זִבְחֵי-צֶדֶק (v'who zeev'chay tzedek) means "the slaughter of sacrifice of righteousness." Bring unto the LORD the offering of a dutiful and righteous life. Then place your full trust in the LORD. One must learn how to "tremble" and rejoice" in the LORD's presence. Do not put your trust in the materialistic world but preferably in the spiritual world.

David said to Absalom's followers that they needed to ask for forgiveness, which requires a sacrifice to achieve atonement.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Give to the LORD sacrifices of righteousness and trust the LORD.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 Many are saying, "Who will show us <i>any</i> good?" Lift up the light of Your countenance upon us, O LORD!	רַבִּים אֹמְרִים מִי יַרְאֵנוּ טוֹב נְסֶה־ עֲלֵינוּ אֹר פְּנֵיךָ יְהוָה :

Verse Analysis

רַבִּים אֹמְרִים (rabeem om' reem) means "many are saying." Many people wish to experience some good. They know that there is only one kind of happiness.

The Shekinah acts in one's life to make one aware of the LORD's presence and keeps us on the right path. The Light of Ein Sof can shine upon all who believe. The Sage Rashi explained that a person should always be content with his/her life if he/she does not look around to find someone living better.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Many people say the Shekinah guides us to mitzvot. May the Light of Ein Sof shine upon us.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 You have put gladness in my heart, More than when their grain and new wine abound.	נְתַתָּה שְׂמֵחָה בְּלִבִּי מֵעֵת דְּגָנָם וְתִירוֹשָׁם רַבּוּ :

Verse Analysis

David said to the LORD that he did not have to beg for happiness because he always had received it from the LORD. The LORD implanted in David's heart the trait of being happy with what the LORD has given.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, you put happiness in my heart from the Spiritual World, which is more than from the Material World.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁸ In peace I will both lie down and sleep, For You alone, O LORD, make me to dwell in safety.</p>	<p>בְּשָׁלוֹם יִתְדוֹ אֶשְׁכַּב וְאִישָׁן כִּי־ אַתָּה יְהוָה לְבַדְּךָ לְבֵטַח תוֹשִׁיבֵנִי :</p>

Verse Analysis

Even though David's enemies surrounded him, his trust was in the LORD, who protected him. David slept comfortably because the Shekinah was with him. The Shekinah felt like a wall surrounding him, so he knew no one could harm him.

The verse can be seen as an appeal for peace and unity.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, give me unity and a place of safety and peace.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory through music, a Psalm of David.

When I pray LORD, I know you will vindicate me because you have taken away my distress in the past.

Sons of great men, how long will you respect the monarchy? You love vanity and seek deception. Pause and meditate on this verse.

Know that Chesed will shower people devoted to the LORD its love and mercy, and Chesed will listen when prayer is offered.

Depart quickly from sinning and sin no more. When you prepare to sleep on your bed, let go of the material world and concentrate on the Spiritual world. Meditate upon this verse.

Give to the LORD sacrifices of righteousness and trust the LORD.

Many people say the Shekinah guides us to mitzvot. May the Light of Ein Sof shine upon us.

LORD, you put happiness in my heart from the Spiritual World, which is more than from the Material World.

LORD, give me unity and a place of safety and peace.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

